

Bidders' Competitiveness in Rural Road Projects in Nepal: A Case Study of World Bank Funded Project

Anjay Kumar Mishra*, N. K. Singh**

* Doctoral Research Scholar, Project Management, Institute of Business Management, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur, India, OrcidID: 0000-0003-2803-4918;
Email: anjaymishra2000@gmail.com

**Associate Professor, Institute of Business Management, Chhatrapati Shahu Ji Maharaj University, Kanpur, India

ABSTRACT:

The comparative study on the trend of competitiveness among contractors before and after the introduction of e-bidding in public procurement in the Rural Transport Infrastructure sector in the local government institutions regarding the number of bids and cost trend of bids has been the core objective set for this research study. The case study of procurement process for civil works in rural roads undertaken by RAIDP in different districts is taken for research.

The bid data with Bid Evaluation Reports of 45 contracts of road projects before and after the launching of E-bidding was sampled for research. The study covers the procurement of road works in more than 15 districts comprise of both *Terai* and Hill out of 30 districts taken by project. The research revealed that bid participation in conventional paper based system was rather abnormal. The bid submission was only 26.84% of the bids purchased. It was found that in one of the worst case, 107 bidders purchased the bids and only 4 bidders had submitted the bids in which only three bids were found to be responsive. The pattern of bid purchasing and submission in case of E-bidding is found to be more consistent. The bid submission was 90.57% of the bids purchased and the participation of electronic bid submission was 57% of the total. The researcher believes that the findings of this study are useful for reviewing the existing provision of public procurement system.

Keywords: *Bidding Trend, Paved Roads, E-bidding, abnormal, bid submission, public procurement etc.*

Background

Competitive bidding is widely applied in many sectors besides construction. Open bidding employs an iterative negotiation process, whereby each contractor independently negotiates a contract price with the client. Consultation among competing contractors is allowed, and contractors are allowed to revise their bid for as long as the client has not come up to a decision on which bid to accept. The open form of bidding is widely used in the commercial sector. Sealed bids on the other hand, are more typical of the construction and civil engineering sector. In sealed bids, each contractor is allowed to submit only one bid, and negotiation between the client and competing contractors is barred. Equally, discussion pertaining to the project under bid between the competing contractors is not allowed. Each contractor's bid is submitted by a specific date, and once submitted cannot be revised. Traditionally, bidding in construction and civil engineering is characterized by two main features. First, there is a large input by the client in detailing requirements for the contract, normally established through consultants in the form of drawings and specifications. Thus, the

essential criterion for evaluating the bids becomes price. Second feature of construction bids is that all the competing contractors bid on the same common information (Harris and McCaffer, 2001, Blackwell Science).

Competitive bidding based on tender documents prepared by the clients' professional advisors is still the most common method of distributing the construction industry's contracts among the contractors willing to undertake the work. Variations such as negotiated contracts and package deals form only a proportion of the contracts offered to the industry. The acceptance by the majority of clients, mainly central and local government, that competitive bidding is fair and will produce the lowest possible commercially viable tender price in the prevailing market conditions, ensures that this form of work distribution will continue for a long time. The random nature of the bidding process also ensures that contracting companies will be unable to plan their company's activities with much certainty: that many contracts will be tendered for with unrealistically low prices and that the pre-occupancy of most contractors with claims will also continue. (Harris and McCaffer, 2001, Blackwell Science)

The construction industry and its clients are widely associated with Bid and Procurement issues in the construction industry. These issues are different depending upon nature of construction business activities, processes, environment and organization. Bid and Procurement is a substantial and integral element of construction project management. It has been the issue of attention in the construction world. Due to time and cost overruns associated with construction projects, so many projects fail to accomplish their targets and objectives. Unmanaged or unmitigated bidding and procurement procedures are one of the fundamental causes of these overruns (Farooqui et al., 2008).

The case study of procurement process for civil works in rural roads undertaken by RAIDP in different districts is taken for research. As stated above, the project has been consistently funded by the World Bank. RAIDP is a follow-on project of the Rural Infrastructure Project (RIP) that was implemented successfully under The World Bank's Learning and Innovation Loan (LIL). This project is under implementation in accordance with the decentralization policy of the Government of Nepal. It is one of the important major projects under MoLD/DoLIDAR. The project was approved in June 21, 2005 with the effective date of implementation of project being on August 16, 2005. As per appraisal document, the project was supposed to be closed on December 31, 2010. There were 20 districts screened as the beneficiary of project. In the meantime, midterm review of the performance of project was assessed. On the basis of findings, it was agreed that the project be extended with the additional financing. The coverage of districts was increased from 20 to 30 overall with the addition of 10 more potential districts. The official effective date of additional financing was on July 14, 2010 with the extended closing date of project as agreed is on December 31, 2013.

In the first phase of project, Standard Bidding Document (SBD) was prepared for civil works rural road contracts. The document was comprised with the SBD for small civil contracts as guided by PPMO with the minor amendments as provisioned under the SBD for small civil contracts of the World Bank. The strengthening in institutional capabilities of the participating

districts was also initiated to meet the overall objective of the project. It was perceived that construction industry was mainly dominated by some big players in the market. The widespread cases of fraudulent, carteling, collusion and corruption in the public procurement process of civil works contract was in practice in the construction industry. The small contracts with packaging and slicing were encouraged so that the conducive environment be made for local bidders. The idea was also to create the competitive market for local bidders so that their knowledge, skills, bidding strategies gets enhanced. The impacts would have been on the improvement in the aspect of contract management and delivery of quality standards of works. It was also expected that fair and transparent behavior is expressed by bidders in this business at local level. This way, goal of getting the best value of public money would have been achieved.

The Governance and Accountability Action Plan (GAAP) was developed for the proposed additional financing of RAIDP is designed to reflect the joint responsibility of the implementing agencies, and the Bank in ensuring good governance and cost effectiveness in project implementation. The governance assessment exercise carried out within the framework of the on-going RAIDP revealed a number of governance inadequacies and issues that need attention in order to ensure successful implementation of RAIDP Additional Financing and successful achievement of its development objective. These include (i) collusion/cartelling among contractors; (ii) intimidation of contractors during the bidding and execution of works; (iii) frequent cost variations and contract extensions; (iv) weak capacity of contractors leading to poor quality of works; (v) frequent and/or substantial variation orders; (vi) poor performance by some contractors; (vii) unequal payment or delayed payment to unskilled labor hired by contractors; and (viii) delayed payment to some contractors by the government agencies. In addition, it has been recognized that some of the governance-related activities that have been used in the on-going RAIDP need either improvement or strengthening, which include (i) accountability within the concerned central and local governments; (ii) the capacity of government agencies to produce quality designs and accurate cost estimates in some of the road contracts; (iii) transparency in procurement decision-making process; and (iv) the selection process of project roads. (RAIDP Additional Financing,GAAP)

It was decided that with the coordination of Department of Roads (DoR) one portal for e-bidding under the jurisdiction of DoLIDAR be established for the option of electronic submission of bids in RAIDP contracts. The same strategy adopted by DoLIDAR could have helped to create a conducive environment for healthy environment for a healthy competition in construction industry. Now the website www.edolidar.gov.np was designed for electronic procurement procedures. It is made mandatory that the bidding document along with the qualification information, Bill of Quantities is uploaded in the website made. The fundamental function of E-procurement web portal of DoLIDAR is designed to facilitate the bidder to submit their bids through e-submission. Proposed alternative for submission of bid through e-submission is supposed to increase transparency, non-discrimination, equality of

access, and open competition. This site provides easy to use internet access for tender information, information on award of contracts and an alternate facility to submit bids through e-submission to all interested bidders as specified in the Instructions to Bidders.

There is provision for the use of electronic medium in public procurement in Public Procurement Act 2006, (Rule 69). It states, “ Notwithstanding anything contained elsewhere in this Act, Government of Nepal may, by publication of a notice in the Nepal Gazette, provide a mechanism that the Public Entity may arrange, through the means of electronic communications, invite a pre-qualification proposal, issue notice of bid invitation, prepare a short list by inviting expression of interest, invite a proposal of consultancy service, transmit bidding or pre-qualifying documents, receive bids, proposals for pre-qualification or consultancy services, Notwithstanding anything contained elsewhere in this Act, Government of Nepal may, by publication of a notice in the Nepal Gazette, provide a mechanism that the Public Entity may arrange, through the means of electronic communications, invite a pre-qualification proposal, issue notice of bid invitation, prepare a short list by inviting expression of interest, invite a proposal of consultancy service, transmit bidding or pre-qualifying documents, receive bids, proposals for pre-qualification or consultancy services, which has to be notified in Nepal Gazette before use.

Research Objectives

- The objective of this research is to assess the Trend of Bidders’ Competitiveness in Rural Road Projects in Nepal: A Case Study of World Bank Funded Project.

Methodology

Study Area

The study area covers different District Technical Offices covered under the RAIDP project. The data covers with random selection of districts evenly covered Terai as well as Hill districts. The selection of bidding data ranges from contract selection for paved roads as well as unpaved roads. The rationale behind selection of district is just an random selection so that the population taken for research covers the entire spectrum of geography of Nepal. The bidding data of 10 different districts selected on the random basis has been taken into account for conventional bidding system.

Study Population

The targeted population consists of professionals, Engineers and Division Chiefs who work for public entity for procurement of public infrastructure projects and have experience in their jobs to the contractor's evaluation, awarding committees, and to the supervisions and management of public construction projects all over Nepal. This research targets, as study population, the contractors involved in construction business, particularly the road projects.

Sample Size

Based on the literature suggested, sample size for the finite population (Kothari & Garg, 2014) as given below is used. Based on this formula, the sample size of the client, key

informants and contractors respondents were calculated for primary level of data. For this purpose desired level of precision (acceptable error) has been taken as $\pm 10\%$ of the true mean with 90% confidence level. Since the variability in the proportion is not known, maximum variability which is 0.5 has been considered.

$$n = \frac{z^2 * p * N}{e^2 * (N-1) + z^2 * p * q}$$

Where,

n = Size of the Sample

Z = The value of standard variate and its value is 1.64 for 90% confidence level

e = Acceptable error, (assumed that the estimate should be within 10% of true value)

p = Estimated proportion of an attribute that is present in the population

q = 1-p

N = Population size

For secondary data, researcher has taken 45 samples in each category of similar works with conventional bidding system and E-bidding system. It is best tried to keep the nature of samples being similar in both cases. The road works categorized as paved roads and unpaved roads have been taken into account to make almost identical representation in both the cases. Throughout the research, researcher has broadly categorized comparative study on two broad spectrum of bidding system adopted for public procurement.

The research data of contracts materialized in districts include Kailali, Banke, Bardiya, Kapilvastu, Rupandehi, Nawalparasi, Bara, Parsa, Mahottari, Dhanusha, Siraha as Terai districts. similarly, districts like Salyan, Palpa, Syangja, Kaski, Dhading, Nuwakot, Makwanpur, Udayapur of Hill districts has also been taken into account. The bid evaluation reports from the World Bank country office were also accessed.

For the questionnaire survey, 30 nos of respondents from client including Key Informants have been selected for stakeholder analysis. Similarly 30 nos. of contractors' representative including Engineers, contractors have been selected as respondents.

For analyzing comparative study on bidding trends and other parameters, researcher has taken equal samples of civil contracts in two different administrative obligations.

A. Conventional paper based bidding system: In this broad category, contract works of rural roads undertaken by RAIDP project has been taken into account for research. The total 45 contracts with different data required for research parameters are separated and extracted. For sub analysis, the sampled contracts for data extraction has been further divided with the type of works intended for award of contract. the road works for pavement are broadly categorized into paved roads and road works having earthwork, structures are broadly categorized as **unpaved roads**.

- B. E-bidding system:** in this broad category, contract works of rural roads undertaken by RAIDP project after the launching of e-procurement portal has been taken into account for research. Again, the total 45 contracts with different data required for research parameters are separated and extracted. For sub analysis, the sampled contracts for data extraction has been further divided with the type of works intended for award of contract. The road works for pavement are broadly categorized into **paved roads** and road works having earthwork, structures are broadly categorized as **unpaved roads**.

Methods of Data Collection

Primary Data Collection

Questionnaire Survey

The researcher explained some issues included in the questionnaire, which were not easily understandable by some contractors.

Composition and experience in road projects of respondents are as follows:

Table 1 Composition of Respondents

SN	Description	Client	Contractors
1	Senior Division Engineer	5	-
2	Engineers	20	8
3	Key Informants	5-	
4	Vendors		5
5	Contractors	-	17
	Total	30	30

Experience of respondents was also accessed by questionnaire which is found to be suitable for research objectives.

Table 2 Experience of Respondents

SN	Experience in road projects	Response	
		Client (No.)	Contractors (No.)
1	up to 10 years	16	18
2	10-15 years	7	5
3	>15 years	7	7

Secondary Data Collection

This research finding is mainly based on the secondary data of concerning project Rural Access and Decentralization Project (RAIDP) funded by the World Bank. The historical and time series data of different road projects implemented through DDCs contributes the major

outcomes of research findings.

During the research, the table with Codes attributes has been used. The capitalized words taken as Code to analyse the data has following meaning in the context of this chapter

- C – represents the conventional bidding system
- E - represents the e-bidding system
- P - represents the contractual works for Paved Roads
- U - represents the cotractal works for Unpaved Roads
- T - represents the contracts of Terai Districts
- H - represents the contracts of Hill Districts

or example, CUPT-1 means the conventional bidding for paved roads in Terai District whereas -1 means the bid data of chronological order. Similarly, EPH-10 means data representing chronological order of 10 of E-bidding system having contract for Paved Road in Hill District.

Specifically, secondary data required for the research were collected from the following sources.

- i. Relevant text books regarding competitive bidding.
- ii. Research papers of World Bank
- iii. Related Acts and Regulations.
- iv. Published and unpublished literature, reports and journals.
- v. Data source from District Technical Offices covering more than 10 different districts
- vi. World Bank Resources and Bid Evaluation Reports (BER) of project

Data Analysis

The percentage below Engineer's Estimate of the bids is calculated for further analysis. The ratio of bid price to the engineer's estimate gives the percentage below estimate. The winning bid, mostly the lowest bid amount, are also assessed with the ratio of Engineers' Estiamte. The frequencies of bids in the defined range of percentage below Engineers' Estiamtat are calculated and presented in the table. For this, frequency distribution tools are used for analysis. Threshold values of bids are assessed in comparative way with the assumption that contractors' overhead as per norms is 15% of the bid amount. The collusive trending of bids are assessed with simple mathematical calculation. (Bista, 2015) suggested the formula to calculate percentage below engineer's estimate.

$$P = \left(1 - \frac{AA}{EA}\right) \times 100 \dots \quad (2)$$

Where,

P = Percentage below engineer's estimate

AA= Agreement amount

EA = Estimated amount

The dispersion of bid values and degree of variability for a particular contract are interpreted with the calculation of Standard Deviation and Coefficient of Variation (%) to reflect the intrinsic quality of bid values among the set of contract data. The statistical formula adopted for this calculation is as follows:

$$\text{Standard Deviation (SD)} = \sqrt{\sum (x-\mu)^2 / (N-1)}$$

Where x = population variant

N = No. of population variant

$$\mu = \text{Mean Value} = (x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + \dots) / N$$

The coefficient of Variation (CV) for particular set of data in percentage is calculated as

$$\text{CV (\%)} = (\text{SD}/\mu) * 100\%$$

Overall trend of bidding in two different bidding environment are found out by plotting the graph between percentage below engineer's estimate and respective contracts. Linear trend lines were adopted for the simplification of data analysis and to understand the nature of the association between these variables. Data Analysis outline is as follows:

Table 3 Data Analysis Outline

S.N.	Description	Bids Received in Conventional Bidding System	Bids received in E-bidding system
1	Bids purchase and submission pattern	Data of 45 sampled contracts	Data of 45 sampled contracts
2	Overall Trend Analysis Pattern Specific parameters for paved road contracts Specific parameter for unpaved road contracts.	Data of 45 sampled contracts	Data of 45 sampled contracts
3	Bids Assessment Against Threshold Values- Normal Bids, Low Bids	Data of 45 sampled contracts	Data of 45 sampled contracts
4	Questionnaire Survey among clients and contractors: responses of respondents are analyzed		

The screening and interpretation of collusive bidding study will use the difference between the engineers' estimated cost and the winning bid price as a tool. Public procurement with a difference between engineers' estimate cost and a winning bid price less than 5 percent are assumed as collusive bids. The research findings also suggest that number of bids less than or equal to 3 for construction in normal circumstances are assumed as collusive trend of bidding. Researcher assumes these two criteria only to detect collusive bidding, even though there are various characteristics of collusive bidding in public procurement.

A structured questionnaire survey approach was used to assess the respondent's attitude or perception about the relative importance of the views of respondents regarding current bidding trend on road projects of DROs and improvement suggestions for better performance of construction projects under study. Likert-type Scale (Summated Scale) was used in analyzing qualitative data obtained from the questionnaires, which is suitable for ranking the statements of respondents' views by using the relative importance index. Likert's scale of five ordinal measures of agreement towards each statement (1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Undecided, 4 =Agree and 5=Strongly Agree) was used to calculate the mean score for each factor which was subsequently used to determine the relative ranking.

The Relative Importance Index (RII) for each variable was computed by using the formula as shown in equation 3.

$$RII = \frac{\sum(f \times S)}{(A \times N)} \dots (3)$$

Where:

- RII = Relative Importance Index
- f = Frequency of responses for each score
- S = Scores given to each factor (from 1 to 5)
- A = the highest weight (equal to 5)
- N = Total number of responses concerning each factor

After ranking of view suggestions of clients and contractors, Charles Spearman's or Rank Correlation coefficient (Kothari & Garg, 2014) is calculated for the analysis of correlation between clients and contractors about views and suggestions.

Table 4 Research Matrix

SN	Objectives	Tools for Data Collection	Data Source	Analysis method	Expected outcome
1	Comparative analysis of the bidding trend of contracts in two different bidding	bidding data, purchasing of bids, submission of bids, responsiveness	RAIDP Projects, District Technical offices	Descriptive, quantitative analysis	information about bidding trends

SN	Objectives	Tools for Data Collection	Data Source	Analysis method	Expected outcome
	environment				
2	to analyze the threshold values of bids in comparative way to define Normal bids and Low Bids	contract data, questionnaire survey, focus group discussion	RAIDP Projects, District Technical offices	Descriptive, quantitative analysis	Bidders competitiveness in the construction business

Trend Analysis

The comparative study of bidding trends before and after commencement of e-bidding and its consequences in rural road projects undertaken by RAIDP projects has been thoroughly analysed and presented. The second part of the chapter presents the analysis and discussion of the qualitative data collected through the responses of clients and procurement experts as Key Informants and contractors working for in different type road projects and other infrastructure projects as a part of questionnaire survey.

Bidding Trend

To analyse with the contract data, the researcher has comprehensively categorized the contract data with the attributes. The comparative analysis of bidding trends in conventional bidding system and e-bidding system in comprehensive discussion and presentation in tabular form has been thoroughly used for bidding trends. Furthermore, the case study of contractual roads with paved category and similarly unpaved roads category are taken as attributable factors governing the bidding behavior. Another attributable factor taken into account is contracts are geographical dispersion separating Terai districts and Hill districts. The rationale behind is the complexity of works associated with these two attributes.

Bid purchase and submission

The trends with purchasing of bidding documents and submission of bid has been assessed comparatively in conventional bidding system and e-bidding system has been discussed and found that the average bid submission as that of bids purchase is only 26.84% and the responsive bids is found to be 86.78% out of the submitted bids. The withdrawal of bids is occasional. In the table above, it is found that in one case 107 bidders purchased the bids and only 4 bidders has submitted the bids in which only three bids are found to be responsive. This could be the classical example of collusive bidding in construction business particularly the procurement for roads construction.

It is found that the average bid submission as that of bids purchase is 90.57% and the responsive bids is found to be 80.88% out of the submitted bids. The withdrawal of bids is again occasional. The participation from bidder through electronic submission of bids is found to be progressive at an average of 57.7% of the total bids submission. The fact remains that bidder prefers to purchase the hard copy version of bidding document available through

office. This is also assessed that responsiveness of bidder despite the e-bidding provision remains on 80.88% of submitted bids.

Variance of Engineers' Estimate and Winning Bid

The comparative assessment in variance of Engineers' Estimate and potential bidder evaluated as substantially responsive lowest evaluated bidder has been worked out.

Case I: Overall contracts of both paved roads and unpaved roads in conventional bidding

In this case, overall trend of variance of Winning Bid with Engineers Bid in conventional bidding system has been assessed and presented.

The calculation shows that the average winning bid is below 13.78 % of Engineers' Estimate in the consideration all contracts of both paved and unpaved types in conventional bidding system. The range of variance below Engineers' Estimate falls from 0.01% to 49.58% in some of the cases. The majority of winning bids comes out to be from -1% to -15% of Engineers' Estimate.

Case II : Contracts for Paved Roads in conventional Bidding system

In this case, trend of variance of Winning Bid with Engineers Estimate in contracts for paved roads has been assessed and presented.

The calculation shows that the average winning bid is below 16.62 % of Engineers' Estimate in case of contracts for paved roads in conventional bidding system. The range of variance below Engineers' Estimate falls from 0.13% to 30.96 % in extreme cases. The majority of winning bids comes out to be either upto 5% below of Engineers' Estimate or more than 15% below of Engineers' Estimate.

Case III : Contracts for Unpaved Roads in conventional Bidding system

In this case, trend of variance of Winning Bid with Engineers Estimate in contracts for unpaved roads has been assessed and presented.

It is concluded from the calculation in the table above is that the average winning bid is below 11.96 % of Engineers' Estimate in case of contracts for unpaved roads in conventional bidding system. The range of variance below Engineers' Estimate falls from 0.01% to 48.37 % in extreme cases. The majority of winning bids comes out to be either upto 5% below of Engineers' Estimate with some contracts having more than 30% below of Engineers' Estimate.

Case IV: Overall contracts of both paved roads and unpaved roads in E- bidding

In this case, overall trend of variance of Winning Bid with Engineers Bid in E-bidding system has been assessed and presented. It is concluded from the calculation in the table above is that the average winning bid is 25.78 % below of Engineers' Estimate in case of contracts for overall sampled road contracts in E- bidding system. The range of variance below Engineers'

Estimate falls from 0.89% to 49.22 % in extreme cases. The majority of winning bids comes out to be above 20% below of Engineers' Estimate with equally distributed contracts having more than 30% below of Engineers' Estimate.

Case V: Contracts of paved roads in E- bidding

In this case, the trend of variance of Winning Bid with Engineers Bid in E-bidding system in contracts for paved roads has been assessed and presented.

It is revealed from the analysis that the average winning bid is below 25.60 % of Engineers' Estimate in case of contracts for paved roads in E- bidding system. The range of variance below Engineers' Estimate ranges from 14 % to 42 % in extreme cases. The majority of winning bids comes out to in the consistent range of around 20% below of Engineers' Estimate

Case VI: Contracts of unpaved roads in E- bidding

In this case, the trend of variance of Winning Bid with Engineers Bid in E-bidding system in contracts for unpaved roads has been assessed and presented.

The analysis reveals that the average winning bid is below 26.08 % of Engineers' Estimate in case of contracts for paved roads in E- bidding system. The range of variance below Engineers' Estimate ranges from 0.89% to 49.44 % in extreme cases. The majority of winning bids comes out to in the consistent range of around 20% below of Engineers' Estimate.

Based on the analysis and the data from the table of six different cases, the researcher has summarized the trend of setting the winning bid with Engineers' Estimate. The values in the table below simply suggest the arithmetic average of variance in winning bid with Engineers' Estimate.

Table 5 Summary of Average Variance from Engineers' Estimate

	Average Variance in %		
	Overall contracts	Paved Road Contracts	Unpaved Road Contracts
Conventional bidding	-14.34%	-16.62%	-11.96%
E-bidding	-25.87%	-25.60%	-26.08%

It is revealed from the analysis that the average winning bid switches from around 12% to 17% in case of conventional bidding system with the complexity in intervention of road works while the average value is consistently around 25% irrespective of the complexity of road works in case of E-bidding system.

Distribution Frequency of Bids Against Variance

The researcher has analysed the range of bidding values and frequency of bidders in two different cases separately. The overall trends with composite case of paved roads and unpaved

roads in conventional bidding as well as E- bidding system has been presented and assessment has been done.

Case I: Overall contracts in conventional bidding system

In this case, overall trend of variance of Winning Bid with Engineers Bid in conventional bidding system has been assessed and presented.

No. of Contracts = 45

Table 6: The frequency distribution of bidders in conventional bidding system

Lower limit	Upper limit	Range (% below Engineers' Estimate	No. of Bidder (f)	Percentage
		Above	35	12.46%
0	5	0-5	68	24.20%
5	10	5-10	13	4.63%
10	15	10-15	24	8.54%
15	20	15-20	26	9.25%
20	25	20-25	27	9.61%
25	30	25-30	27	9.61%
30	35	30-35	20	7.12%
35	40	35-40	19	6.76%
40	45	40-45	13	4.63%
45	50	45-50	9	3.20%
50	55	50-55	-	0.00%
55	60	55-60	-	0.00%
Total Bidders =			281	100%

It is revealed from the above analysis that almost 25% of bidders tend to bid in the range of 0-5 % below of Engineers' Estimate in conventional bidding system. The next majority bids for above the Engineers' Estimate.

Case II: Overall contracts in E-bidding bidding system

In this case, overall trend of variance of Winning Bid with Engineers Bid in conventional bidding system has been assessed and presented.

No. of Contracts = 45

Table 7: The frequency distribution of bidders in E- bidding system

Lower limit	Upper limit	Range (% below Engineers' Estimate)	No. of Bidders (f)	Percentage
		Above	33	11.15%
0	5	0-5	41	13.85%
5	10	5-10	18	6.08%
10	15	10-15	31	10.47%
15	20	15-20	41	13.85%
20	25	20-25	25	8.45%
25	30	25-30	24	8.11%
30	35	30-35	34	11.49%
35	40	35-40	23	7.77%
40	45	40-45	15	5.07%
45	50	45-50	9	3.04%
50	55	50-55	1	0.34%
55	60	55-60	1	0.34%
Total Bidder			296	100%

It is revealed from the above analysis that 13.85% of bidders tend to bid in the range of 0-5 % and 15-20% below of Engineers' Estimate constituting slightly more than 25% of the total bidders in E-bidding system. There are reasonable numbers of bidders at about 11.15% who tend to bid above the Engineers' Estimate.

Derivation of Threshold Values and Assessment of Bids

The bid amount is assessed on the basis of prevailing Norms adopted for rate analysis of items of works which are used for official estimate. We are aware that in construction business the departmental Norms are designed to take 15% of basic rate as overhead amount for derived rate taken as unit cost of items of works. The overhead amount also includes the profit margin of bidder. Based on that, the researcher tried to analyse the bid amount with the noble assumption that the bid amount less than 15% of Engineers' Amount shall be taken as normal bids. It is tried to establish the threshold value of Normal bids and low bids. The ratio of normal bids and low bids in both the cases of conventional bidding system and E-bidding system is verified with the sampled data of 45 contracts in each case.

Case I: Overall bid data in Conventional bidding system

The data extracted from conventional bidding system has been presented in the following

table for analysis and verification.

Table 8 Assessment of bids for overall contracts in conventional bidding system

Lower limit	Upper limit	Range	Mid value(X)	No. of contracts (f)	U= (X-A)/5	fxU
0	5	0-5	2.5	24	-2.5	-60
5	10	5-10	7.5	3	-1.5	-4.5
10	15	10-15	12.5	-	-0.5	0
15	20	15-20	17.5	3	0.5	1.5
20	25	20-25	22.5	-	1.5	-
25	30	25-30	27.5	3	2.5	8
30	35	30-35	32.5	7	3.5	25
35	40	35-40	37.5	1	4.5	5
40	45	40-45	42.5	2	5.5	11
45	50	45-50	47.5	2	6.5	13
Total				45		-2.5

Average percentage of Bidding Amount (y) = $O + \frac{\sum fxU}{\sum f}$ in %

$$= 15 + (-2.5)/45$$

$$= 14.94 \%$$

It is revealed from the analysis that the contract with 14.94% below the Engineers Estimate is the threshold value to be adopted for Normal Bids and Low Bids. Based on the calculation and analysis, bids up to 14.94 % are normal bids and bids more than 14.94 % are low bids. Considering all the 45 contracts of conventional bidding system , 27 bids (60 %) are supposed to be as Normal Bids and 18 bids (in respective contracts are normal bids and 18 bids (40%) in respective contracts are low bids.

Case II: Bid data for Paved Roads in Conventional bidding system

The data extracted from conventional bidding system for only paved roads has revealed from the analysis that the contracts of this category, 15.28% below the Engineers Estimate is the threshold value to be adopted for Normal Bids and Low Bids. Based on the calculation and analysis, bids up to 15.28 % are normal bids and bids more than 15.28 % are low bids. Considering all the 23 contracts of this category, 11 bids (52 %) are supposed to be as Normal Bids and 12 bids (48%) in respective contracts are low bids.

Case III: Bid data for Unpaved Roads in Conventional bidding system

The data extracted from conventional bidding system for only contracts of unpaved roads has revealed from the analysis that the contracts of this category, 14.59% below the Engineers Estimate is the threshold value to be adopted for Normal Bids and Low Bids. Considering all the 22 contracts of this category, 16 bids (73 %) are supposed to be as Normal Bids and 6 bids (27%) in respective contracts are low bids.

Case IV: Bid data for Overall Contracts in E- bidding system

The data extracted from conventional bidding system for overall contracts in E- bidding samples has revealed from the analysis that the contracts of this category, 17.16% below the Engineers Estimate is the threshold value to be adopted for Normal Bids and Low Bids. Based on the calculation and analysis, bids up to 17.16 % are normal bids and bids more than 17.16 % are low bids. Considering all the 45 contracts of this category, 11 bids (24 %) are supposed to be as Normal Bids and 34 bids (76%) in respective contracts are low bids.

Case V: Bid data for Paved Roads Contracts in E- bidding system

The data extracted from conventional bidding system for paved roads contracts in E- bidding samples has revealed from the analysis that the contracts of this category, 17.05% below the Engineers Estimate is the threshold value to be adopted for Normal Bids and Low Bids.. Considering all the 20 contracts of this category, 4 bids (20 %) are supposed to be as Normal Bids and 16 bids (80%) in respective contracts are low bids.

Case VI: Bid data for Unpaved Roads Contracts in E- bidding system

The data extracted from conventional bidding system for unpaved roads contracts in E- bidding samples has

revealed from the analysis that the contracts of this category, 17.26% below the Engineers Estimate is the threshold value to be adopted for Normal Bids and Low Bids.. Considering all the 20 contracts of this category, 7 bids (28 %) are supposed to be as Normal Bids and 18 bids (72%) in respective contracts are low bids.

The researcher tried to summarize the assessment of sampled contract values against the threshold bid prices with respect to percent below of Engineers' Estimate in three different cases each in conventional bidding system as well as in E- bidding system. The threshold values, the proportion of Normal Bids and Low Bids in both bidding system has been presented in the following table.

Table 9 Summary Assessment of Bid Values Against Engineers' Estimate

	Conventional Bidding					E-bidding				
	Threshold Value %	Normal Bid		Low Bid		Threshold Value %	Normal Bid		Low Bid	
		No.	%	No.	%		No.	%	No.	%
Overall	14.94	27	60.00	18	40.00	17.17	11	24.44	34	75.56

Paved	15.28	11	47.83	12	52.17	17.05	4	20.00	16	80.00
Unpaved	14.59	16	72.73	6	27.27	17.26	7	28.00	18	72.00

CONCLUSIONS

The outcome of the study based on the historical time series data analysis reveals the following conclusions;

- There is a wide gap between Engineers' Estimates and bidders' bid price in rural road projects in Nepal. It is found that most of the bidders tend to focus on low bidding or simply to take the works in hand.
- The range of variance –(20to 30)% was observed to be very common in bidding for unpaved roads with civil structures in case of conventional bidding system.
- The range of variance –(10to 25)% was observed to be very common in bidding for paved roads with in case of conventional bidding system.
- The range of variance –(25 to 35)% was observed to be very common in bidding for unpaved roads with civil structures in case of electronic bidding system.
- The range of variance –(15to 30)% was observed to be very common in bidding for paved roads with in case of electronic bidding system.
- The proportion of Normal bids and Low bids in conventional bidding system is almost 60 % to 40% while in E- bidding it is 25% to 75%
- The E-bidding system promotes the Low Bidding.
- Further study for collusive bidding and stakeholder need to be conducted.

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